

CERTIFICATE

OF APPRECIATION

TIBBIYOT AKADEMIYASI

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Narbaev K.P.

PATHOGENETIC TREATMENT OF CHRONIC TONSILLITIS WITH

FUNGAL BACTERIAL INFECTION

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI

WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

